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Study of Some Reactions on Acetophenone Derivatives II

V. M. GURAV and U. K. JAGWANI*

Department of Chemistry, Yeshwant College, Nanded 431 602, Maharashtra State, India

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IN continuation of our previous work¹ some reactions on acetophenone derivatives (5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone)² have been studied.

The oxime of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone when treated with phosphorus oxychloride gave an acetanilide derivative which on hydrolysis with dilute sulphuric acid gave the known amino derivative³.

5-Chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone when treated with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate at 190° for 10 hr gave 3-benzoyl derivative which on alkaline hydrolysis led to the known 6-chloro-flavone⁴. Similarly when heated with acetic

anhydride and fused sodium acetate at 190° for 10 hr it gave the product to which 3-acetyl-6-chloro-2-methylchromone structure was assigned. The above product on hydrolysis shows the characteristic peaks for chromone⁵ at 1650; 1600; 1776; 1378 cm⁻¹. The characteristic peaks for coumarin at 1737 for δ -lactone and 1668 cm⁻¹ for (-C=C-CO-) were absent. 5-Chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone on condensation with benzaldehyde in the presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide gave chalkone. It showed yellow colouration to the Wilson test⁶ and isomerised to 6-chloroflavone when the ethanolic solution was refluxed with phosphoric acid for 12 hr.

5-Chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone on heating with ethyl acetoacetate at 130° for 1½ hr in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid gave the product to which 8-acetyl-6-chloro-4-methyl coumarin structure was assigned on the basis of IR data (the characteristic peaks for coumarin at 1737 for δ -lactone and 1668 cm⁻¹ for (-C=C-CO-)).

Experimental

Oxime of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone(I), acetanilide derivative(II), 2-amino-4-chlorophenol(III); 3-benzoylflavone(IV); 6-chloroflavone(V); 3-acetyl-6-chloro-2-methyl chromone(VI), 6-chloro-2-methyl chromone(VII), chalkone derivative(VIII) and 8-chloroflavanone(IX) were prepared according to the procedure described¹ (Table 1).

8-Acetyl-6-chloro-4-methyl coumarin(X) was prepared by heating a mixture of 5-chloro-2-hydroxy acetophenone (3.2 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (3 ml) in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid (10 ml) on oil bath at 130° for 1½ hr. The reaction mixture was left overnight, poured over crushed ice, the solid product separated was crystallised from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (40-60°) in white needles.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS

Nos.	Molecular Formula	M.P.* °C	Yield %	Physical Property	Analysis percentage							
					C		H		Cl		N	
					Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.	Found	Cal.
I	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ ClN	180	60	White needles	52.3	51.75	4.8	4.3	19.17	19.14	7.5	7.54
II	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ ClN	183	35	Pale brown needles	52.0	51.75	4.7	4.31	18.7	19.14	7.5	7.54
III	C ₈ H ₆ OCIN	138	50	Brown shining plates	50.28	50.13	4.31	4.18	24.44	24.74	9.97	9.57
IV	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	190	50	White needles	73.0	73.33	3.47	3.61	10.2	9.86	—	—
V	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	172	50	Yellow needles	70.5	70.17	4.4	3.58	13.28	13.84	—	—
VI	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	134	60	White	60.3	61.06	4.3	3.8	15.34	15.01	—	—
VII	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	147	30	White	61.58	61.69	3.4	3.59	18.51	18.25	—	—
VIII	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	112	50	Yellow	69.6	69.65	4.25	4.09	14.6	13.73	—	—
IX	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	183	60	White	69.6	69.65	4.25	4.09	13.28	13.73	—	—
X	C ₁₇ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	184	38	White	61.23	61.06	3.96	3.8	15.54	15.01	—	—

* All the mps are uncorrected.

* Present Address: Chemistry Department, University of Arkansas, Pine-Bluff, Arkansas 71601, U.S.A.

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Chemical Investigation of the Roots of *Phyllanthus niruri*

J. S. CHAUHAN*, MOHD. SULTAN and S. K. SRIVASTAVA
Chemistry Department, Allahabad University, Allahabad
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EARLIER communication¹ from this laboratory reported the isolation and characterization of two new glycoflavanones from the roots of *Phyllanthus niruri*. The plant is reputed for its medicinal importance.²

The air dried and powdered root of *P. niruri* was extracted with ethanol under reflux for 125 hr. The total ethanolic extract was kept in a refrigerator which deposited a white crystalline compound (0.92 g). Petroleum ether extract of the deposit gave a white amorphous mass (0.8 g) containing two compounds (TLC examination). These two compounds (designated as A and B) were separated over neutral alumina column, eluted with C_6H_6 : $CHCl_3$ (6 : 4 v/v) and C_6H_6 : $CHCl_3$ (2 : 8 v/v).

Compound-A, $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 442), m.p. 211-12°, (α)_D²⁵ +27° (in $CHCl_3$) gave positive LB test for triterpenes. This was characterized as Lupa-20(29)-ene-3- β -01 by m.p., m.m.p., Co-IR and Co-TLC with an authentic sample of lupeol.

Compound-B, $C_{32}H_{50}O_2$ (M^+ 466), m.p. 213-14°, (α)_D²⁵ +50° (in $CHCl_3$) also gave a +Ve LB test for triterpenes. Alkaline hydrolysis of the compound-B gave an alcohol, identified as lupeol (Co-TLC and Co-IR)^{3,4} and CH_3COOH . Detailed study of the compound-B showed it to be the acetate of lupa-20(29)-ene-3- β -01 (confirmed by Co-TLC and Co-IR).

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Chemical Investigation of *Gerbera lanuginosa* Benth (whole plant) and Leaves of *Ipomoea fistulosa* Mart

(Miss) MANJU SEN, (Mrs.) MANJUSRI DEY
and
PRADIP KARURI

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 295

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IPOMOEA fistulosa Mart (Convolvulaceae) is a South American plant migrated to India. Prolonged ingestion of this plant results in wasting, depression and other ill-defined pathology in sheep, cattle and goats.¹ From the leaves of the plant previous worker² reported the isolation of some fatty acid glycosides. Our present communication reports the isolation of β -sitosterol from the leaves of the same plant.

Dried and powdered leaves of the plant were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) for 10 hrs. The crude residue on chromatographic separation over silica-gel yielded a white crystalline solid, m.p. 133-137°, which on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine furnished the corresponding acetate, m.p. 128-130° (Lit³ m.p. 127-128°), identical (m.m.p., T.L.C., and I.R.) with an authentic specimen of β -sitosteryl acetate. The benzene and ethylacetate extracts of the plant on chromatographic separation yielded no crystalline solid.

Gerbera lanuginosa Benth (Compositae) grows in the temperate Himalayas at the altitude of 4000-9500 ft. The white cotton like coating found under the surface of the leaves is used for straining wounds and is also used for making coarse cloth⁴. Since no chemical investigation on this plant has so far been reported we were interested to undertake a systematic chemical examination of the plant.

Dried and powdered whole plant of *G. lanuginosa* was successively extracted with (A) petroleum ether (60-80°) and (B) benzene. The petroleum ether